

Problems encountered in implementing collaborative pedagogy and ways to overcome them

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ANNOTATION

In the implementation of collaborative pedagogy, there are problems such as lack of cooperation between teachers, parents, and the community, difficulties in focusing on the individual student, and delays in teachers' adaptation to new methods. To solve these problems, effective cooperation can be established by ensuring the active participation of parents and the community, providing continuous training to teachers, and using person-centered, creative approaches.

Keywords: Collaborative learning, socio-psychological environment, collaborative relationships, education, team teaching, small group teaching, independent thinking.

In the modern rapidly changing information world, the search for optimal approaches and teaching methods is one of the pressing issues. Among the existing approaches, a noteworthy approach is cooperative pedagogy. This direction, which emerged in the mid-80s of the 20th century, is a system of teaching and upbringing methods, based on the principles of dialogue, humanism and a creative approach to personal development. It is based on a deep understanding of the student's personality and a humanistic approach, collective education, high professionalism of the teacher and public attention to the educational institution. The ideas of cooperative pedagogy were expressed by the educator Simon Lvovich Soloveitchik. Cooperative pedagogy was based on a completely different view of the educational process: instead of the traditional dominance of the teacher, it implied a transition to a situation of cooperation between students.

Main part.

Cooperative pedagogy implies such a level of the educational process, in which its objects and subjects are united in common activities by the principles of mutual respect, mutual assistance and solidarity. Its main principles are interaction, cooperation, partnership, humanism, creativity, personal development, solidarity, joint activity, dialogue and mutual enrichment.

The main idea of cooperative pedagogy is teaching without coercion. In this process of interaction, the main attention is paid to involving the student in the educational process, the joint work of the teacher and the student in a team and the individual process of mastering new skills.

The essence of the method is that it is based not on the classical principles of "do as I say" and "do as I do", but on the principle of "let's think together about how it can be done". It is this approach that allows the student to instill responsibility and adjust the process of active learning. Traditional education is based on the position of the teacher as the subject, and the student as the object of the pedagogical process. In the concept of cooperation, this rule is replaced by the idea of the student as the subject of educational activity.

It is based on the fact that two subjects of one process work together, on the cooperation of a less experienced student and an experienced teacher, in which neither of them should be superior to the other. In this case, the student can confidently express his ideas and feel the necessary support in solving complex problems.

The idea of free choice allows the development of the student's individual characteristics. The teacher must set a difficult goal for students, show its extreme complexity and be sure that the goal will be achieved. Freedom of choice is the easiest and at the same time most effective way to develop creative thinking. The student can set himself a task that he is interested in solving. With this, he develops thinking and expands his boundaries.

The traditional education system is usually aimed at forming a solid set of knowledge in students, which is a standard form of education. As a rule, such an attitude does not imply an individual approach to the development of the student's creative qualities, taking into account the individual characteristics of the student.

Collaborative pedagogy involves the use of modern, interesting forms and means of education, such as games, discussions, brainstorming, team competitions, etc. Teachers and educators who adhere to the concept of cooperative pedagogy strive to make the student a co-author of the lesson in their lessons, instill confidence in him and get rid of a sense of fear. They also take into account the psychological characteristics of a particular person, accepting him as an individual, not as part of a group.

Another principle of cooperative pedagogy is the teacher's communication with students, a friendly and attentive attitude to their views, encouraging ideas and thoughts, even bad or incorrect, cooperation in developing activities and finding solutions. The goals and objectives of the course and curriculum are formed through dialogue between partners, during which the desired results are determined, the curriculum itself and even the learning strategy are improved and updated.

At first glance, cooperative pedagogy may seem like an easy concept to understand and implement. However, this is far from the truth. The success of its implementation depends on the work of both parties - the teacher and the students. Learning how to relate to other people is an important part of cooperative pedagogy.

For many teachers, the main difficulty in applying the concept of cooperation is that it assumes a sufficient level of interaction between the two parties. So, for example, not every teacher could find an individual approach to the student. Not all children had an open and flexible character, so they were not ready for an open and sensitive exchange of ideas. The principle of cooperation implies a responsible attitude to the process from both sides. The teacher must learn to take into account the opinion of absolutely any member of the group. Even the most passive-minded participant has the right to openly express his point of view on a particular issue, and the teacher's task is to help all participants come to an agreement and reach an agreement.

As a tool of cooperative pedagogy, games, stories, conversations on acute social issues, discussions, exchange of experiences, meetings with famous people, finding solutions, brainstorming and much more can be used. However, in order to successfully use these tools, the teacher must first learn to think holistically, skillfully combining all effective methods in his practice. To achieve the desired result, the teacher must use not only the usual methods and means of conducting classes in his work, but also take the initiative, using creative thinking and communication skills. His task is to build the educational process so that each of its members is as involved as possible in it without losing interest and inspiration.

Another difficulty on the way to the transition to a new form of interaction is the state of modern pedagogical practice, namely: insufficient pedagogical support from both teachers and students; general dissatisfaction with the educational process; lack of an individual approach to students; unwillingness of teachers to change their fundamental position in relation to students; lack of innovative teaching technologies and education aimed at developing the personality of students.

Therefore, cooperative pedagogy is very difficult to implement in most educational institutions that are accustomed to operating according to old schemes. However, this does not mean that it is impossible to implement. The ability to negotiate and find a common language with each member of the group is the main task for any teacher. However, excellent communication skills are useful not only for teachers and educators, but also for everyone who in one way or another comes into contact with other people.

Conclusion.

Despite all the difficulties that arise, this style of interaction between the teacher and students has proven to be effective. The main idea of cooperative pedagogy is to overcome the inertia of thinking and make the learning process as humane and democratic as possible. With the opportunity to openly express their personality, each student can use their strengths and develop their weaknesses.

The opportunity to participate in open communication with the teacher and other students allows you to train communication skills, expand boundaries, exchange ideas and views, which undoubtedly leads to growth and development. Respect for all participants in the learning process, without exception, allows you to show more individuality and creativity in solving even the most difficult problems. Setting a common goal for each member of the team makes the process of achieving it as effective and at the same time interesting as possible. The opportunity to choose allows each student to take responsibility for their own education only on their own.

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